

Study on Social Media Addiction and Its Effects on Academic Performance and Mental Health among College Students

Dr. Radha Mishra¹

¹Assistant Professor, Kamla Nehru B.Ed. Girls College, Satna (M.P.) INDIA

Abstract: *Social media has become an integral part of students' lives, profoundly influencing their mental health. This research paper investigates the phenomenon of social media addiction and its effects on academic performance and mental health among college students. As social media platforms become integral to students' daily lives, understanding the potential adverse effects of excessive use is crucial. The findings aim to provide insights into the implications of social media addiction and suggest strategies for mitigating its negative impacts on students' academic and mental well-being.*

Keywords: Social Media, Mental Health, Study, Academic Performance.

Introduction:

Social media has emerged as a critical platform for communication in recent years. It allows users to effortlessly share data, files, pictures, and videos, as well as post blogs, send messages, and engage in real-time chats regardless of distance. Over the past decade, checking and scrolling through social media has become a common activity for people across all demographics. The advancement of information technology has made internet access more convenient than ever. Social media dependence (SMD) is characterized by a behavioral reliance on social media, driven by an uncontrollable urge to use it, and dedicating excessive time and effort to it, which can detract from other important life areas. The impulse to express oneself on social media activates the same part of the brain that responds to addictive substances. There is a clear link between social media use and negative physical and mental health outcomes, as well as low self-esteem, which has been exacerbated by the pandemic.

In recent years, social media has become an integral part of daily life, particularly among college students. Platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and TikTok serve as primary means for communication, entertainment, and information dissemination. While social media offers numerous advantages, including the ability to maintain relationships, access educational resources, and engage in social activism, its pervasive use has raised concerns about its potential negative impacts.

One of the most pressing issues is social media addiction, characterized by excessive and compulsive use of social media platforms, often to the detriment of other important activities and responsibilities. College students, who are in a critical phase of personal and academic development, are especially vulnerable to the lure of social media. The constant need to check notifications, post

updates, and engage with online content can lead to significant time management challenges, negatively impacting academic performance. Furthermore, the psychological effects of social media addiction, including anxiety, depression, and stress, are increasingly becoming a topic of concern among educators, parents, and mental health professionals.

Literature Review:

- 1. Positive Impacts of Social Media:** Social Support and Connection: Social media enables students to maintain relationships, form new connections, and receive social support, which can alleviate feelings of loneliness and enhance overall well-being (*Ellison, Steinfield, & Lampe, 2007*).
- 2. Access to Information and Resources:** Platforms like YouTube and LinkedIn provide educational content, career advice, and mental health resources, empowering students with knowledge and support (*DeAndrea et al., 2012*).
- 3. Opportunities for Self-Expression:** Social media allows students to express themselves creatively, share their experiences, and engage in discussions about their interests, contributing to a sense of identity and self-esteem (*Michikyan, Subrahmanyam, & Dennis, 2014*).
- 4. Social Media Addiction:** Social media addiction is characterized by excessive and compulsive use of social media platforms, leading to negative consequences in an individual's life. Studies have shown that social media addiction is associated with various psychological and behavioral issues, including reduced academic performance and poor mental health (*Kuss & Griffiths, 2017*).
- 5. Academic Performance:** Research indicates that excessive use of social media can negatively impact students' academic performance. Time spent on social media can reduce the time available for studying, attending classes, and completing assignments, leading to lower grades and academic achievement (*Kirschner & Karpinski, 2010*).
- 6. Mental Health:** Social media addiction has been linked to various mental health issues, including anxiety, depression, and stress. The constant need to stay connected, fear of missing out (FOMO), and exposure to cyberbullying and negative feedback can contribute to poor mental health outcomes (*Andreassen et al., 2016*).

Negative Impacts of Social Media:

- 1. Anxiety and Depression:** Excessive use of social media is linked to increased levels of anxiety and depression among students, often due to comparison with others, cyberbullying, and negative feedback (*Primack et al., 2017*).

2. **Cyberbullying:** The anonymity and reach of social media can facilitate cyberbullying, which has severe psychological effects on victims, including low self-esteem, anxiety, and suicidal thoughts (*Kowalski, Giumetti, Schroeder, & Lattanner, 2014*).
3. **Addiction and Sleep Disruption:** Social media addiction can lead to poor academic performance, disrupted sleep patterns, and overall mental fatigue, negatively impacting students' mental health (*Andreassen et al., 2016*).

Significance of the Study:

Understanding the impact of social media addiction on college students is essential for several reasons. Firstly, academic institutions and educators can benefit from insights into how social media usage patterns affect students' academic outcomes. Secondly, parents and guardians can better support their children by recognizing the signs of social media addiction and encouraging healthier online behaviors. Lastly, mental health professionals can develop targeted interventions to address the psychological impacts of social media addiction, promoting overall well-being among students.

Scope and Limitations:

This study focuses on college students aged 18-25 from various colleges and universities. The mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews, aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the issue. However, the study is limited by its reliance on self-reported data. Additionally, the findings may not be generalizable to all college students, as social media usage patterns and their impacts can vary widely based on cultural, social, and individual factors.

Research Objectives:

1. To study the prevalence of social media addiction among college students.
2. To study the impact of social media addiction on academic performance.

Research Methodology:

1. **Research Design:** This study employs a mixed-method approach, combining quantitative surveys and qualitative case studies to explore the impact of social media on students' mental health.
2. **Participants:** The participants include 150 students from various colleges and universities, aged 18-25. They were selected using random sampling to ensure a diverse representation of social media usage patterns.
3. **Data Collection:** Online surveys were conducted to gather quantitative data on social media usage, mental health status, and perceived impact. In-depth interviews and case studies were conducted with a subset of participants to gain qualitative insights into their experiences with social media.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:**Section “A” - DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION****Table-1
Demographic Profile**

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age		
18 – 20 Years	65	43.33
21 – 23 Years	45	30.00
24 – 26 Years	32	21.33
27 and above	8	5.33
Total	150	100
Gender		
Male	90	60.00
Female	60	40.00
Others	0	0.00
Total	150	100
Year of Study		
1 st Year	64	42.67
2 nd Year	41	27.33
3 rd Year	38	25.33
4 th Year	7	4.67
Total	150	100

Source: Survey in 2024

Interpretation: The demographic profile of the respondents, as presented in Table 1, indicates that the majority of participants are aged between 18 and 20 years (43.33%), followed by those aged 21 to 23 years (30%), and a smaller representation from the 24 to 26 years (21.33%) and 27 and above (5.33%) age groups. Gender distribution reveals a predominance of male respondents (60%), with females comprising 40% and no representation from other genders. Regarding the year of study, the highest proportion of respondents are first-year students (42.67%), followed by second-year (27.33%), third-year (25.33%), and fourth-year students (4.67%). This demographic data provides a foundational understanding of the respondent base for the study on social media addiction and its impact on academic performance.

Section “B” - SOCIAL MEDIA USAGE PATTERNS**Table-2**
Social Media Usage Patterns

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
How many hours do you spend on social media per day on average?		
Less than 1 Hours	10	6.67
1 – 2 Hours	38	25.33
2 – 3 Hours	45	30.00
3 – 4 Hours	55	36.67
More than 4 Hours	12	8.00
Total	150	100
Which social media platforms do you use regularly?		
Facebook	43	28.67
Instagram	43	28.67
Twitter (Now X)	22	14.67
LinkedIn	17	11.33
Others	25	16.67
Total	150	100
Do you use social media during class or study hours?		
Yes	91	60.67
No	59	39.33
Total	150	100

Source: Survey in 2024

Interpretation: The data in Table-2 reveals significant insights into the social media usage patterns among college students. A majority of students (66.67%) spend between 2 to 4 hours per day on social media, with the highest percentage (36.67%) spending 3 to 4 hours daily. Only a small fraction (6.67%) spend less than an hour, and 8% spend more than 4 hours. In terms of platform preference, Facebook and Instagram are equally popular, each used by 28.67% of students, while Twitter (now X) and LinkedIn are less common, used by 14.67% and 11.33% respectively. Additionally, 60.67% of students admit to using social media during class or study hours, indicating a prevalent integration of social media into their academic routines.

Section “C” - INDICATORS OF SOCIAL MEDIA ADDICTION**Table-3
Indicators of Social Media Addiction**

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
How often do you feel the urge to check your social media accounts?		
Never	20	13.33
Rarely	22	14.67
Sometimes	56	37.33
Often	37	24.67
Always	15	10.00
Total	150	100
Do you feel restless or irritable when unable to access social media?		
Never	12	8.00
Rarely	31	20.67
Sometimes	28	18.67
Often	30	20.00
Always	49	32.67
Total	150	100
How often do you neglect personal or academic responsibilities due to social media use?		
Never	13	8.67
Rarely	29	19.33
Sometimes	39	26.00
Often	29	19.33
Always	40	26.67
Total	150	100

Source: Survey in 2024

Interpretation: The data in Table-3 highlights significant indicators of social media addiction among the surveyed college students. A notable 37.33% of students sometimes feel the urge to check their social media accounts, with 24.67% and 10.00% reporting often and always feeling this urge, respectively. When unable to access social media, 32.67% of students always feel restless or irritable, and 20.00% often experience these feelings, indicating high levels of dependency. Additionally, social media use leads to the neglect of personal or academic responsibilities, with 26.67% of students always and 19.33% often admitting to this behavior. These findings suggest a prevalent issue of social media addiction, impacting both the emotional well-being and academic responsibilities of college students.

Section “D” - ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE, SELF-ASSESSMENT AND PERCEPTIONS

Table-4
Academic Performance, Self-Assessment and Perceptions

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Have you noticed a decline in your grades or academic performance over the past year?		
Yes	98	65.33
No	52	34.67
Total	150	100
Have you ever missed deadlines or failed to complete assignments on time due to social media usage?		
Yes	105	70.00
No	45	30.00
Total	150	100
Do you believe social media use affects your concentration during study sessions?		
Strongly agree	49	32.67
Agree	37	24.67
Neutral	24	16.00
Disagree	29	19.33
Strongly disagree	11	7.33
Total	150	100
Do you feel that your social media use is excessive?		
Yes	94	62.67
No	56	37.33
Total	150	100
Have you sought help or considered seeking help to manage your social media usage?		
Yes	110	73.33
No	40	26.67
Total	150	100

Source: Survey in 2024

Interpretation: The data in Table-4 reveals significant insights into the impact of social media on the academic performance and perceptions of college students. A notable 65.33% of students reported experiencing a decline in their grades or academic performance over the past year, indicating a widespread perception of negative academic impact. Additionally, 70.00% admitted to missing deadlines or failing to complete assignments on time due to social media usage, further highlighting the detrimental effect on academic responsibilities.

Concerning concentration during study sessions, a combined 57.34% (32.67% strongly agree and 24.67% agree) of students believe that social media use adversely affects their focus. In terms of self-assessment, 62.67% of students feel their social media use is excessive, suggesting a high level of self-awareness about their usage habits.

Moreover, a significant 73.33% of students have either sought help or considered seeking help to manage their social media usage, underscoring a recognition of the issue and a willingness to address it. These findings collectively underscore the pervasive influence of social media on students' academic lives and their acknowledgment of its impact.

Findings:

1. A significant majority (65.33%) of students have noticed a decline in their grades or academic performance over the past year, indicating a substantial negative impact of social media usage on academic outcomes.
2. 70.00% of students reported missing deadlines or failing to complete assignments on time due to social media use. This suggests that social media addiction leads to procrastination and poor time management among students.
3. Over half of the respondents (57.34%) believe that social media use affects their concentration during study sessions. This points to the disruptive nature of social media on students' ability to focus on their academic work.
4. 62.67% of students feel that their social media use is excessive. This indicates a high level of self-awareness regarding their social media habits and its potential impact on their academic and personal lives.
5. A significant portion (73.33%) of students have either sought help or considered seeking help to manage their social media usage. This reflects a recognition of the problem and a proactive attitude towards addressing it.

Suggestions:

1. Universities and colleges should conduct workshops and seminars to educate students about the potential negative impacts of excessive social media use on academic performance. Raising awareness can help students make more informed choices about their social media habits.
2. Institutions should offer time management and productivity training to help students develop better study habits and reduce procrastination. Techniques such as the Pomodoro Technique or digital detox strategies can be introduced.
3. Establish or strengthen counseling services that specifically address issues related to social media addiction. Providing students with access to professional help can assist them in managing their usage more effectively.
4. Encourage students to set boundaries for social media use, such as designated “no social media” times during study hours. Developing apps or tools that help track and limit social media usage could also be beneficial.
5. Form peer support groups where students can share their experiences and strategies for managing social media use. This community approach can provide mutual support and accountability.
6. Promote the use of educational technology and apps that enhance learning and academic performance. Encouraging students to use social media for academic collaboration and communication can help integrate it positively into their lives.

7. Implement regular assessments to monitor students' academic performance and social media usage patterns. Providing feedback and personalized recommendations can help students stay on track.

Conclusion:

The study highlights the significant impact of social media addiction on the academic performance of college students. The findings indicate that a majority of students experience a decline in grades and miss academic deadlines due to excessive social media use. Additionally, many students recognize the disruptive effect of social media on their concentration and admit to excessive usage. The willingness of a large number of students to seek help underscores the severity of the issue and their recognition of its negative consequences.

Addressing social media addiction requires a multifaceted approach involving awareness, education, and support from educational institutions. By implementing targeted interventions such as time management training, counseling services, and peer support groups, colleges and universities can help students develop healthier social media habits. Encouraging a balanced digital environment and integrating technology positively can also mitigate the adverse effects on academic performance. Through these efforts, institutions can support students in achieving their academic potential while managing their social media use responsibly.

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About the Author

Dr. Radha Mishra

Dr. Radha Mishra is a distinguished academic and researcher in the field of Sociology. Currently, she serves as an Assistant Professor at Kamla Nehru B.Ed. Girls College in Satna. She completed her Ph.D. in Sociology from Mahatma Gandhi Chitrakoot Gramodaya University, Chitrakoot, Satna (M.P.). With a profound dedication to research, Dr. Mishra has amassed extensive experience over the years. Her scholarly work has been widely recognized, with numerous research articles published in reputed national and international journals. Her contributions to the field of Sociology have not only advanced academic understanding but also influenced contemporary social research paradigms. Dr. Mishra's expertise and commitment to education make her a valuable asset to the academic community. She continues to inspire and mentor students and peers alike, fostering a vibrant environment for learning and research at Kamla Nehru B.Ed. Girls College